

Evaluation of True Streaming Potential of Diaphragms ; Each Containing Glass Spheres of a Given Size

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It has been shown that the true streaming potential of soft glass particles can be evaluated by applying surface conductance correction alone to the experimental data of Schriever and Bleil on four diaphragms, each containing particles of a given radius, bathed in water and also in $10^{-5} M$ NaCl solution at 27° .

IN a paper published in 1957 on "streaming potential in uniform grain sands" Schriever and Bleil² concluded from their experimental results (i) that the observed (V/p) (where V is the potential in mV and p the pressure in cm of water) was independent of change in the configuration of sand matrix as well as changes in its porosity and (ii) that the variation in (V/p) with grain diameter was only partially accounted for by surface conductance alone.

Our attention to this paper was drawn only recently and we would like to point out that the conclusions (i) and (ii) of the aforesaid authors¹ are based on inadequate data and on neglect of the effect of porosity of a diaphragm on its apparent streaming potentials $(V/p)_a$.

In a series of papers published previously, a few³⁻⁶ of which are referred to here, it has been shown by us that the true zeta potential, ζ , or the true streaming potential (V/p) of diaphragms formed by particles of graded size of any given material can be found by introducing proper correction for surface conductance. Starting with the accepted principle that at constant temperature the electrokinetic potential and specific surface conductivity of the particles of a given material in contact with a given solution remain constant, equations of the following form were deduced³⁻⁵.

$$\zeta/\zeta_a = 1 + \frac{3\chi}{a r s} \quad \dots (1)$$

where ζ and ζ_a represent the true and apparent zeta potential respectively, χ the specific surface conductance of the particles, a the phase volume ratio of liquid to solid in the diaphragm the packing of which should be uniform, r the radius of the particles forming the diaphragm and s the specific conductivity of the liquid.

The corresponding equation for the true and apparent streaming potential denoted by (V/p) and $(V/p)_a$ respectively may be written as

$$(V/p)/(V/p)_a = 1 + \frac{\alpha\chi}{r s} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$= 1 + \frac{\alpha m}{r} \quad \dots (2a)$$

where $\alpha = 3/a$ and $m = \chi/s$.

When the phase volume ratio in the diaphragm remains constant and its packing is uniform α remains constant, and m remains constant when s is kept constant. Hence under conditions in which α and m remain constant and only r is varied, a plot of $(p/V)_a$ against $1/r$ should be linear and equation (2a) may be used in the following form :

$$(p/V)_a = (p/V) + \alpha m (p/V) \frac{1}{r} \quad \dots (3)$$

Analysis and processing of the data :

Schriever and Bleil used only four "sands" (i.e. spherical particles of soft glass) of diameter 300, 175, 153, 147 microns, respectively in preparing the diaphragms. They did not record in their paper the cell constants of the diaphragms, the specific conductivities of water and of the solutions of the electrolytes used by them.

They stated in para 2 under the head "Results" in page 172 of their paper that for water $(V/p)_a$ was 42.5 mV/cm of water for the diaphragm containing sands of diameter 300 microns, while from Fig. 2 of their paper¹, $(V/p)_a$ was found to be 51.3 mV/cm of water for a diaphragm made of 'sands' of the same diameter (i.e. 300 microns). It, therefore, follows that their measurements on $(V/p)_a$ were reproducible within about 18%.

They also investigated the effect of porosity on $(V/p)_a$ using three diaphragms packed to porosities 0.432, 0.411 and 0.392 and found that $(V/p)_a$ was constant within the reproducibility of the measurements of these three packings.

It may be pointed out that in their experiments the variation of porosity from the average value 0.411 lay within $\pm 5\%$ only. Since the reproducibility gap in their measurements was large, about 18%, the effect of this small change of $\pm 5\%$ in porosity on $(V/p)_a$ could not be detected by them and hence they neglected it completely. It is this that led them to the erroneous conclusions mentioned above.

The data of Schriever and Bleil at 27°, collected from Fig. 2 of their paper¹, are recorded in this paper in Tables 1 and 2 and are also represented graphically in Fig. 1 by plotting $(p/V)_a$ against $1/r$.

are bathed in water and 0.006 when they are bathed $10^{-6}M$ NaCl solution. The points representing D(4) in the $(p/V)_a$ vs $1/r$ diagram (Fig. 1) lie above the straight lines mentioned above. However, the true (p/V) of D(4) must also be 0.004 in water and 0.006 in $10^{-6}M$ NaCl solution since it is made of the same glass as the other three diaphragms. Its difference in behaviour from the other three is to be attributed to its packing represented by α_4 being more compact than α representing the packing of the other three diaphragms. The values of α_4 mp/V of the straight lines joining the points representing D(4) with the corresponding points representing true (p/V) in Fig. 1 are found to be 5.84 in water and 6.28 in $10^{-6}M$ NaCl solution. The values of α mp/V of the other three diaphragms are 4.74 in water and 5.08 in $10^{-6}M$ NaCl solution. Putting these values of α mp/V in equation (3) the values of $(p/V)_a$ of the three diaphragms have been calculated and recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The agreement between the observed and calculated values of $(p/V)_a$ is quite satisfactory.

It is also to be noted that the ratio of $(\alpha_4 \text{ mp/V}) / (\alpha \text{ mp/V})$ is the same (i.e. 1.23) both in water and in $10^{-6}M$ NaCl solution indicating that the packing of D(4) relative to that of the other three diaphragms does not change in the two sets of experiments.

In conclusion it may be stated that the true (p/V) of the glass particles used by Schriever and Bleil can be found by using equation (3) which deals with surface conductance correction only.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF $(p/V)_a$ WITH $1/r$ Diaphragm bathed in water at 27°

Miscellaneous	Diaphragm No.	$1/r$ in microns ⁻¹	Values of apparent $(p/V)_a$	
			Observed	Calculated
Eqn. (3) $(p/V) = 0.004$ α mp/V of each of D(1), D(2), D(3) = 4.74 α_4 mp/V of D(4) = 5.84 $\alpha_4/\alpha = 1.232$	D(1)	0.00333	0.0195	0.0198
	D(2)	0.0057	0.0315	0.031
	D(3)	0.0065	0.035	0.035
	D(4)	0.0068	0.043	0.037 (using α mp/V = 4.74) 0.044 (using α_4 mp/V = 5.84)

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF $(p/V)_a$ WITH $1/r$ Diaphragm bathed in $10^{-6}M$ NaCl at 27°

Miscellaneous	Diaphragm No.	$1/r$ in microns ⁻¹	Values of apparent $(p/V)_a$	
			Observed	Calculated
Eqn. (3) α mp/V of each of D(1) D(2) and D(3) = 5.08 α_4 mp/V of D(4) = 6.28 $\alpha_4/\alpha = 1.236$	D(1)	0.00333	0.0225	0.0229
	D(2)	0.0057	0.0350	0.0348
	D(3)	0.0065	0.0390	0.0390
	D(4)	0.0068	0.049	0.041 (using α mp/V = 5.08) 0.049 (using α_4 mp/V = 6.28)

In column 1 of the two Tables under the head miscellaneous are mentioned the equation used, the value of true (p/V) , the value of α mp/V of the three diaphragms D(1), D(2), D(3) and also the value of α_4 mp/V of the diaphragm D(4).

Results and Discussion

It will be noticed from Fig. 1 and also from the data recorded in Tables 1 and 2 that variation of $(p/V)_a$ with $1/r$ is linear for the three diaphragms D(1), D(2) and D(3) and the intercept of the straight line on the $(p/V)_a$ axis is 0.004 when the diaphragms

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